

Metadata Document for Dataset Submission:

Determining Monolignol Oxifunctionalization by Direct Infusion Electro spray Ionization Tandem Mass Spectrometry

Title:

Determining monolignol oxifunctionalization by direct infusion electro spray ionization tandem mass spectrometry

Authors of the Data:

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Release Date:

2024-05-08

Folder Content Description:

This dataset includes raw measurement files, mass spectrometry intensity values mapped against m/z values, processed data tables and figures, and supplementary documentation.

Origin of the Data:

Data were collected as part of the NewCat project conducted at the Norwegian University of Life Sciences. Enzyme selection was provided by bisy GmbH (Wuenschendorf, Hofstätten an der Raab, Austria).

Research Methods Used:

High-throughput flow injection analysis combined with direct infusion electro spray ionization tandem mass spectrometry (DI-ESI-MS/MS) was used for the rapid identification and quantification of native and oxifunctionalized monolignols. Enzyme selection involved screening a broad panel of unspecific peroxygenases (UPOs) from bisy GmbH. Biocatalytic conversion of lignin model compounds was assessed under standardized assay conditions.

Time Range of Data Collection:

2022-06-21 to 2024-01-24.

Research Area:

Analytical chemistry, method development, biocatalysis, and enzymology.

Data Owner:

The Norwegian University of Life Sciences

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Horizon Europe Funding:

- **Project Name:** Teaching Lytic Polysaccharide Monooxygenases to do Cytochrome P450 Catalysis
- **Acronym:** NewCat
- **Grant Number:** 101046815
- **Funding Program:** EIC Pathfinder program
- **Call Identifier:** HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01

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Persistent Identifiers for Related Publications and Research Outputs:

- DOI for related publication: 10.1039/D4AY00403E
- Data DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15773150

Search Keywords:

Lignin, monolignols, oxifunctionalized lignin compounds, flow injection analysis, electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry, high-throughput screening, selected ion monitoring, analytical method development, quantitative analysis, mass spectrometry, unspecific peroxxygenases, biocatalysis.